

Role of Early Surgical Intervention in the Acute Appendicitis: A Prospective Analysis

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Accurate diagnosis of acute appendicitis based on symptoms is essential in minimizing morbidity and mortality associated with perforation and other complications. This study aimed to explore the important factors that surgeons take into account when making decisions regarding suspected appendicitis cases.

Material and Methods: The study included a total of one hundred patients, with a predominance of male participants. During the operation, the surgeon described the macroscopic appearance and assessed the severity of the appendicitis using the grading scale established by Ditillo and colleagues in 2006. We closely monitored important parameters, including the duration from hospital arrival to surgery (HI) and the total interval (TI), which measures the time from the onset of symptoms to the surgical procedure. Patients who presented with an intra-abdominal abscess or perforated appendicitis during surgery received extended courses of antibiotics after the procedure.

Results: Significant correlation was observed between higher pathology grades and older age ($p = 0.001$). The mean temperature recorded was 37.26 degrees Celsius, falling within the range of 37.06 to 38.1 degrees Celsius. Notably, a significant correlation was observed between temperature and the advanced pathological degree. A positive correlation was observed between the prevalence of advanced pathology and prolonged PI, which varied from 25 to 40 hours.

Conclusion: The decision-making process in cases of suspected appendicitis is largely based on a systematic approach. This approach involves the use of "hard" data, such as the results of laboratory tests and the findings of radiological investigations, which play a significant role.

Keywords: Acute Appendicitis, Perforation, Temperature.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis (AA) represents one of the most frequently encountered urgent surgical conditions. The overall incidence stands at about 86 cases per 100,000 patients annually, with the highest occurrence of non-perforated appendicitis observed in adolescents and young adults aged 13 to 40 years. Perforated appendicitis occurs in approximately 19% of cases, showing a bimodal distribution that primarily affects both children and the elderly population. [1,2]

Appendicitis is derived from Latin, where it combines the terms appendix and -itis, indicating an inflammation of the appendix. The term appendix originated in the 1540s to refer to an elongated outgrowth of an internal organ. Appendicitis was first described in 1759 by Metieuer. At that time, it was thought that the appendix was not the source of the disease process, leading to terms such as perityphlitis, typhlitis, paratyphlitis, or extra-peritoneal abscess of the right iliac fossa. [3] Beginning in the early 20th century, appendicitis has

been understood to arise from an obstruction that causes the appendix to secrete fluids. A preliminary investigation revealed, through the use of a manometric recording device (Figure 1), that increased pressures were associated with observable histological changes, including hypercellularity and an exudate pattern linked to appendicitis. It has been reported that early mortality associated with appendicitis stands at 26%. [4,5]

Accurate diagnosis of acute appendicitis based on symptoms is essential in minimizing morbidity and mortality associated with perforation and other complications. The clinical signs of appendicitis include abdominal pain, fever, loss of appetite, and vomiting. Typically, the pain begins in the upper abdomen and then shifts to the right lower quadrant. In ideal conditions, surgeons strive to achieve high sensitivity, minimizing the number of overlooked appendicitis cases. It is essential to aim for high specificity while minimizing the number of negative explorations. [5,6]

Recent discussions have raised important considerations about the adequacy of merely making the correct diagnosis. It is essential to assess whether the condition is a gangrenous appendicitis that might resolve on its own or a progressive appendicitis that poses a significant risk of perforation. The surgeon is expected to accurately diagnose the condition and appropriately stage it, even when working with limited information. [7]

Numerous studies have explored various diagnostic methods for appendicitis, yet only a limited number have examined the cognitive processes that guide the decision to proceed with an appendectomy. This study aimed to explore the important factors that surgeons take into account when making decisions regarding suspected appendicitis cases.

Materials and Methods

This study is a forward-looking analysis conducted on all patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis at the affiliated medical college and hospital. The study included a total of one hundred patients, with a predominance of male participants. Prior to participating in the study, patients received a thorough explanation of the research project and provided their consent by signing a form.

Individuals under the age of 16, those who could not remember the exact onset of their symptoms, and those who showed no indications of appendicitis upon pathology examination were not included in the study. Prior to surgery, each patient underwent an ultrasound or computed tomography scan to validate the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. This was completed prior to the execution of the operations.

A personal interview was conducted and recorded to assess the duration between the onset of symptoms and the patient's arrival at the hospital.

During the operation, the surgeon described the macroscopic appearance and assessed the severity of the appendicitis using the grading scale established by Ditillo and colleagues in 2006. Appendicitis can be classified into different grades based on its severity. Simple appendicitis is categorized as G1, while phlegmonous appendicitis is classified as G2. Gangrenous appendicitis is assigned G3, and the most severe form, perforated appendicitis, is designated as the fourth grade. A pathologist conducted a thorough examination of all specimens included in the study.

We closely monitored important parameters, including the duration from hospital arrival to surgery (HI) and the total interval (TI), which measures the time from the onset of symptoms to the

surgical procedure. Antibiotics were promptly administered to all patients upon receiving a diagnosis of appendicitis. Patients who presented with an intra-abdominal abscess or perforated appendicitis during surgery received extended courses of antibiotics after the procedure. At our hospital, we consistently utilize a laparoscopic approach as the primary method for performing appendectomies. If the surgeon assesses that the laparoscopic procedure is unsafe or no longer viable, they can opt for open conversion at any point during the operation.

Statistical analysis

For categorical parameters, we employed the chi-square test as established by Pearson. A p value of less than 0.05 indicates that the results are statistically significant. The data was generated using SPSS software, version 15.01.1, which was developed by SPSS Inc. in 2006.

Results

A total of one hundred patients participated in the study. A total of 62 males and 38 females were in attendance. The study included patients whose ages varied from 20 to 70 years old. The findings indicated that there was no significant relationship between gender and the severity of pathology ($p = 0.46$). However, a significant correlation was observed between higher pathology grades and older age ($p = 0.001$). The mean temperature recorded was 37.26 degrees Celsius, falling within the range of 37.06 to 38.1 degrees Celsius. Notably, a significant correlation was observed between temperature and the advanced pathological degree, with a p-value of 0.001. A recorded average temperature of 38.1 degrees Celsius was noted at the grade 3 level.

Our research findings indicate that the parameters assessed during the physical examination, including abdominal tenderness and peritonitis, showed no correlation with the severity of the underlying pathology. All patients included in the study exhibited abdominal tenderness, and the symptom of peritonitis was noted in the majority of them.

A positive correlation was observed between the prevalence of advanced pathology and prolonged PI, which varied from 25 to 40 hours. The results indicate that with a p value of 0.03, the average time allocated for grade 1 was 28 hours, whereas for grade 4, it was 38 hours. The same positive relationship was observed regarding the TI, with the time range extending from 35 to 70 hours. Conversely, the observed interval for grade 1 was 38 hours, while for grade 4, it was 58 hours, with a confidence level of 0.02.

Table 1: Relationship between physical examination parameters and the degree of pathology

Parameters	G1	G2	G3	G4
No. of patients	24	55	12	9
Fever	37.02	37.56	37.98	38.02
Abdominal Tenderness	22	52	09	9
Peritonitis	15	38	86	9

Discussion

Each year, over 300,000 appendectomies are performed in the India. It's important to note that less than ten percent of these surgeries conclude with the removal of a normal appendix. Appendicitis is a condition that is believed to occur due to luminal obstruction, which can arise from various factors.

This blockage results in heightened mucus production and an increase in bacterial growth, which can ultimately lead to increased wall tension, tissue death, and the risk of perforation. [8,9] Prompt and precise identification of acute appendicitis can significantly lower the risks of complications such as perforation, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes and reducing associated morbidity and mortality rates. In evaluating the accuracy of a diagnosis, it is essential to consider the individual signs and symptoms, as they play a crucial role in confirming its validity.

The appendix can be found in different locations within the body, leading to various clinical presentations. This variation complicates the process of diagnosis. [10,11]

In less than half of the cases presented, we observed the common pattern of central pain radiating to the right iliac fossa, often accompanied by symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and loss of appetite. Abdominal pain is a prevalent symptom observed in patients. Localized peritonism may intensify in pain during certain movements, including coughing or driving on uneven surfaces. [12] Patients may report a history of feeling generally unwell, experiencing weakness, and having sensations of coldness and clamminess. Individuals may also report any symptom that aligns with sepsis. A meta-analysis of clinical presentations of appendicitis has identified migratory pain as the symptom most closely associated with an acute appendicitis diagnosis. [13]

The degree of pathology is closely linked to the duration between the onset of symptoms and the time of hospital arrival, as well as the interval from symptom onset to the appendectomy procedure. The results align with the conclusions previously established through retrospective studies. It is important to perform an appendectomy promptly after confirming the diagnosis. [14,15] Our research findings indicate that a greater pathological degree correlates with an extended length of hospital stay and a higher occurrence of complications.

It is advisable to proceed with an appendectomy at the earliest opportunity, based on our findings that indicate a positive relationship between the severity of the pathology and both the overall time interval and the patient-specific interval. It is important to note that the timing of the surgery may be influenced by the hospital's resources, particularly while the patient is undergoing antibiotic therapy as part of the pre-surgical preparation.

Conclusion

It has been discovered that the decision-making process in cases of suspected appendicitis is largely based on a systematic approach. This approach involves the use of "hard" data, such as the results of laboratory tests and the findings of radiological investigations, which play a significant role. The evaluation of signs and symptoms has a lesser impact on the decision-making process.

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